

“Understanding the impact of financial literacy on financial wellbeing: A systematic literature review”

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Abstract

Purpose – To make a Competitive financial decision in the growing complexity of financial markets and products, an investor need financial literacy. So this systematic review will provide the critical examine of the connection between the financial literacy and financial wellbeing with the focus on how financial outcomes has improved for the individuals and families by increasing their financial knowledge, abilities, and practices.

Methodology – The research as five significant areas of financial wellbeing, effects of financial wellbeing, effectiveness of financial education for financial wellbeing, obstacles to raise the financial literacy. In this research it examines empirical research from a range of socioeconomic and geographic contexts to emphasize the different aspects of financial literacy, including debt management, investment decision-making, budgeting, and saving, and their effects on financial well-being. Totally 35 research articles were taken for the study in the field of financial literacy impact on financial well-being of the individuals from which it is categorised in the themes and filtered the articles into 25 according to the impact factor more than 1.

Research Gap: Despite the growing focus on teenager financial education, less is known about how early financial literacy teaching influences adults' financial well-being. This study recommends more research on how financial literacy improves financial decision making, savings and investment behavior, debt management, budgeting, and financial control.

Findings: Financial well-being and financial literacy are significantly positively correlated, according to the findings, which also show that financially knowledgeable people have better long-term financial stability, less financial stress, and more financial control.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Financial Well-Being, Debt Management, Investment Decision-making.

Paper type: Literature Review

Introduction

The capacity to make sound financial decisions is one indicator of financial literacy. By detailing their income, expenses, and debts, a person may use this information to build a strategy for reaching financial independence. Owners of small enterprises are also impacted by this matter. To foster expansion and security in the economy, they are fundamental.

In today's sophisticated economic environment, financial literacy is becoming progressively recognized as an essential skill. It refers to having the knowledge and proficiency to use a variety of financial abilities, such as debt management, investing, saving, and budgeting. Fundamentally, financial literacy helps people make sense of financial systems and products that may otherwise be difficult or confusing by giving them the information and self-assurance they need to make sensible financial decisions and with the growth of credit products, investment possibilities, digital banking tools, and retirement plans, people are expected to handle their money more sophisticatedly than ever before as the global financial environment gets more complex. The degree of financial literacy varies greatly among communities, though, and is frequently influenced by variables including income,

education, and access to financial resources. The lack of financial literacy has serious repercussions for financial well-being as people who are not financially literate are more likely to experience debt accumulation, unstable finances, and limited financial security over time.

The importance of financial literacy and how it impacts people's financial well-being is being more and more acknowledged. Having enough financial knowledge has become a critical factor in determining people's overall financial well-being in an era marked by complex financial decisions and economic uncertainties. The ability to understand financial concepts, manage assets, and make informed financial decisions has become increasingly important as financial landscapes and individual financial responsibilities change. In order to understand the underlying mechanisms that may influence people's financial security and contentment, this investigation explores the complex relationship between "financial literacy and financial well-being,".

Research questions

- How is the Concept of Financial Literacy Understood in relation to Individual of Overall Financial Well-being
- Which aspects of Financial Literacy will be including the ability to make effective financial decisions, Enhanced Savings and Investment behaviour, Debt Management, Budgeting and Financial Control.

Literature Review

The Study’s Literature can be effectively organized into Four distinct and comprehensive themes which is listed below

Theme – 1: Conceptualisation of Financial Literacy

Theme – 2: Impact of Financial Literacy on Financial wellbeing of Financial Decision-Making

Theme – 3 : Impact of Financial Literacy on Financial wellbeing of Enhanced Savings & Investment Behaviour

Theme – 4 : Impact of Financial Literacy on Financial Well Being of Effective Debt Management

Theme – 5 : Impact of Financial Literacy on Financial Well Being Better Budgeting and Financial Control

Methodology

The study approach followed a step-by-step integrative systematic review methodology as guided by the procedure of Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria, which included

1. Developing the Inclusion Criteria
2. Identification and Selection of the relevant articles
3. Classification of the selected articles

After the completion of above steps conducting the analysis according to the research questions and identifying the findings of the study. The research papers were picked up from the Quality Journal, Google Scholars, academia etc. Articles with the title "Impact of Financial literacy on Financial wellbeing" were found from a search using the keyword. The Inclusion and Exclusion criteria of the systematic study is based on the following aspects

Fig. 1. The Systematic Literature Review Study Strategy of (1) Fig.1

Table 1

Summary of search strings and Boolean Operators

Filters	Search Strings	Boolean Operators
Search “Intitle and Abstract” & “Intext” Keywords for the Period 2019 – 2024	Conceptualization of Financial Literacy Impact of financial literacy on Financial Well Being	Financial Literacy And / Or Impact of Financial Literacy on Financial Well Being

Selection of Databases and Journal Articles

The databases were chosen from the interdisciplinary studies, from which 35 peer-reviewed publications in all were processed. Table 1 above provides a summary of some of the keywords used in combination to find the related articles. The expectations of the study questions guided the selection of key phrases utilized in the search. A mixture of the several search terms was used in the first searches, producing 32,324,693 and 34,024,529 research papers in total which is shown in Table 2.

The PRISMA 2020 framework was used in the development of the literature review process. To make sure that no prior systematic review on the same subject had been undertaken, a preliminary Internet search was conducted. This was carried out in compliance with the compiled quality controls.

This was carried out in compliance with the table 3 summary of quality controls. This reduced the likelihood of duplication and increased the likelihood of publication to 856,821.

Table 2

Summary of data selection Process

Information about the search	Financial Literacy	Impact of Financial literacy on financial wellbeing
Total Preliminary Results	112,784,762	118,441,102
Restriction (by Period)	2019 – 2024	2019 – 2024
Results	32,324,693	34,024,529
Research Articles	543,849	856,821
Articles Selected from the period (2019 to 2025)	6	29
Eliminated (Under the criteria of impact factor which were less than 1)	2	8
Articles Selected for the Study	4	21

Quality Control

After careful consideration, 25 articles were included in the data set and organized on a spreadsheet according to the topics covered by the research questions. Despite developments involving the transmission of research material, a significant amount of research typically went unreported, as the study also acknowledged. Accordingly, in order to strengthen the credibility of the systematic review findings, the study team examined essential older literature. Most systematic reviews have some degree of bias, therefore this one made an effort to reduce that risk as much as possible, as seen in Table 3. As a quality control measure, we relied on data supplied from reliable databases and journals with an impact factor of 1 or higher. The study team also consulted the college library and an information and communications technology (ICT) expert to assist with data extraction.

Table – 3

Quality Control Measures adopted during the Study

Quality Control Measure	Risk Minimization Measure
The literature review followed a quality control guide.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before beginning the search, investigated internet databases to make sure no previous work had addressed the same concerns & also made sure for qualifying criteria to clear and had been peer-reviewed. • Relevant databases were looked through to find relevant literature. • Online search techniques were reviewed by experts to ensure objectivity.

Data analysis

Because spreadsheets allowed for large amounts of data and allowed researchers to avoid interfering with the phenomena of commercialization, this method was used to analyse the literature. It was useful for quantitative and qualitative textual analysis. To fill these knowledge gaps, we reviewed a number of studies that discussed the conceptualization of financial literacy and its effect on the financial well-being of individuals. The reason this method was chosen ahead of others was that it adequately addressed all of the study questions.

Results and Discussion

The results from the data collected were tabulated and categorized in terms of Author& Year of Publication, Methodology, Contributions, Research Limitations, Practical Implications, Results.

Author and year of Publication	Title of the Paper	Design / Methodology / Approach	Contributions	Research Limitations / Implications	Practical Implications	Originality / Value / Results
Theme – 1: Conceptualisation of Financial Literacy						
Dr. Vikas Mahadule, Mrs. Harsha Patil, Mr. Pavan Padghan, Mr. Saurav Temgire (5 th November 2024)	Financial Literacy in India	The variables that impact the degree of financial literacy are investigated.	A person's degree of financial literacy is affected by their education, income, and access. So Offers suggestions to improve financial literacy programs.	Education and income are two Barriers to improving financial education in India.	Recommendations for strengthening financial education in India. Tackle obstacles to effectively promoting financial literacy.	Examination of the present level of financial literacy in India is undertaken. Examines effects on individual financial stability and the state of the economy.
Suhail Ahmad Bhat, Umer Mushtaq Lone, S. Arunkumar, U M Gopal Krishna (13 th November 2024)	Digital Financial Literacy and Financial Well – being evidence from India	Method of collecting data through surveys using questionnaires. Structural equation Modeling and confirmatory factor analysis for analysis.	Makes recommendation s for courses that teach people how to handle their own money.	Financial well-being is negatively impacted by impulsivity.	Students' digital financial literacy may be improved through educational programs. Streamline the personal financial operations online.	Having self-control has a good effect on financial well-being, while impulsivity has the opposite effect.
Jyothi Prakash Rath April 2023	Financial Literacy in India – A New Way Forward	Study made from the secondary source and research design was descriptive method	Importance as to create for the different types of Financial Services available in India	Every Individual may not be interested to get the knowledge / education of financial services	If people can understand the financial services benefits, then they may be in good financial well-being	Significance for Financial Literacy and Financial Services available in India
Rajesh Mishra 2022	Financial Literacy and Financial Wellbeing among Indian Households	The survey made of 47,132 Indian Households taken from the Financial Inclusion Insights Survey, waver 5, Conducted by Intermedia	Management regression analysis suggests that monetary attitude, knowledge (objective and subjective), and practices predict financial well-being.	Financial behavior influenced by an individual's overconfidence in their own subjective financial knowledge	A person's financial well-being is greatly affected by their level of financial education, attitude, and behavior.	Knowledge, attitude, and behavior towards money are the three best indicators of a person's financial well-being.
Theme – 2: Impact of Financial Literacy on Financial well-being of Financial Decision Making						
Mishra, Deepak, Naveen, Agrawal, Sanawi Sharahiley and Vinay Kandpal (17 th October 2024)	Digital Financial Literacy and its Impact on Financial Decision – Making of Women: Evidence from India	Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used to analyse 385 responses from women in India. Examined correlations between financial factors and decision-making affects.	Government initiatives aimed at empowering women to make better financial decisions.	Women lack enough knowledge about digital finance. Obstacles in using digital financial systems successfully.	To empower women economically, we must increase their digital financial literacy. Encourage more women to use financial technology by implementing government programs.	Women's financial liberation requires knowledgeable financial decision-making. Financial decisions strongly influence a woman's investment desire.
Zaara Chowdhury (01 st November	Determinants of	Based on Some factors which	Provides an emphasis on	A lack of education makes	Financial literacy among young	Improved financial literacy

2024)	financial literacy of adolescents in India and its impact on their decision making	Researchers emphasize the need for targeted financial management education programs for youth	specific initiatives to increase financial literacy.	it harder to make well-informed decisions.	people requires focused efforts to Educate themselves on the many financial resources available in the market.	requires focused efforts.
Dr. P. Chandrika Reddy, Shafiya Taj (8 th August 2024)	The Impact of Financial Literacy on Personal Financial Decision – Making: A Study Among Students	Information gathered from 100 participants using questionnaire by using a convenience sample method.	Incorporating programs that teach youngsters about personal finance improves their financial security in the long run.	Learning is impacted by a lack of access to resources for financial education.	Help students become better managers and decision-makers with their money.	Students' long-term financial security is enhanced by implementing financial literacy programs.
Sonam Rani 14 th Sep 2023	The Impact of Financial Literacy on Financial Well-Being: The Mediation Role of Personal Finance Management	Collected information from various studies of research from the year 2010 to 2023	It compiles research results and highlights the importance of personal financial management as a moderating variable.	It is associated with more financial behaviours, retirement planning decisions, and many more	Importance of Targeted Financial Education Interventions.	Financial education and interventions empower people by giving them the knowledge and confidence to handle their finances.
Mubarakah Bunyamin, Nor SHaipah Abdul Wahab 30 th December 2022	Impact of Financial Literacy on Finance and Economy: A Literature Review	Review of the various studies were undertaken from the year period of 2018 - 2022	The article focuses at the potential of financial technology (FinTech) to improve financial literacy.	Only Few studies have examined the effect of financial literacy on company growth.	Financial technology has the power to increase both financial literacy and competence.	Cash advances are associated with a lack of financial knowledge.
Suresh G 23 rd August 2021	Impact of financial literacy and behavioural biased on Investment Decision making	Study on financial literacy and behavioral biases on investment decision using questionnaire and SEM.	When it came to making decisions, heuristic bias was positively associated with the development of behavioral bias.	Collection of the data from the investors and making them understand about the financial literacy	As an alternative to more incorrect decision-making strategies, investors frequently engage in and commit to heuristic biases.	Decisions to invest in the stock market are heavily influenced by the level of financial knowledge of individual investors.

Author and year of Publication	Title of the Paper	Design / Methodology / Approach	Contributions	Research Limitations / Implications	Practical Implications	Originality / Value / Results
Theme – 3: Impact of financial literacy on financial well-being of enhanced savings and investment behaviour						
Bangun Putra PRasetya 31 st July 2023	The Effect of Financial Literacy on Financial Well – Being mediated by Financial Behaviour	Quantitative Research using the PLS SEM Analysis Tool	Influence of Financial Literacy variables on Financial Behaviour Variables and Financial behaviour Variables on Financial Well Being		The influence between the Financial Literacy Variables on Financial Well Being is stated to be Significant	The effect of Financial literacy on Financial well being will be Significant if mediated by Financial Behaviour
Seema Gupta 14 th April 2023	Financial Literacy, Savings and Investment Behaviour of IT Professionals	The primary survey analysis of 90 IT professionals was conducted using a structured questionnaire.	People’s ability to understand and manage their own finances is by their Financial Literacy	There is a wide range of investment goals, from achieving financial stability to generating additional income.	IT Professionals Desire Safe and Liquid Investments	The Importance of Perceived Financial Knowledge in Making Investment Decisions

Godfred Matthew Yaw Owusu, Theodora Aba Abekah Koomson, (Et., Al) 14 th Jan 2022	Savings and investment behaviour of young adults – the role of financial literacy and parental financial behaviour	Survey based approach and Employed Covariance – Based Structural Equation Modeling Technique to examine the Hypothesis	Financial Literacy Positively Correlates with savings and Investment Behaviour of Young Adults	Many of the Young Investors are still depends on their parents to make any investments	The degree to which young individuals are financially literate is directly correlated with how their parents manage their own finances.	There was a favorable correlation between young adults' financial literacy and their investment behaviors.
Dr. Sukhpreet K Thind, Dr. Asim Ray 2023	Evaluating the impact of financial literacy program on Investment behaviour – A Survey study	A survey approach was used in the study, which included varied demographics to ensure an extensive analysis.	There was a marked decrease in the use of informal advice and an increase in the use of consistent, diverse investing strategies among the participants.	The data collected from the selected area which may vary the response from the other areas	The authors of the research emphasize the need of financial education in the classroom, say that financial data should be regulated, and call for program customization.	Acquiring strong financial knowledge is essential for making wise investment decisions.
Godfred Matthew Yaw Owusu, Theodora Aba Abekah Koomson, (Et., all) 11 th August 2023	The Nexus amongst Financial Literacy, Financial Behaviour and Financial Well-being of Professional Footballers in Ghan	In a cross-sectional survey of 300 Ghana Premiere League footballers, we evaluated hypothesized relationships using partial least squares structural equation Modeling.	Financial education, behavior, and wellbeing study has focused on industrial professionals. Professional players' viewpoints enrich this study.		The financial knowledge and conduct of footballers is very lacking. The findings demonstrate that enhancing players' financial knowledge encourages prudent financial practices.	Financial literacy, behavior, and wellness research have primarily focused on industrial workers. This publication uses professional players' expertise.
Wagar Younas, Muhammad Farooq, (et, al) 20 th Jan 2019	Impact of Self - Control, Financial Literacy and Financial Behaviour on Financial Well - Being	Quantitative Study with A Survey Conducted on 416 people from educational institutions, Corporate Sectors and Food courts in Pakistan	The Study examines the relationship between Self – Control Financial Literacy, Financial behaviour, and Financial Wellbeing	Empirical Examine on impact of Self Control and Financial Literacy on Financial Behaviour and Financial Well-being of the people	Financial Literacy has a significant direct impact on Financial Well-being, However the direct impact of Sel-control on Financial Well-being is Insignificant	The Effect of Financial Wellbeing Is More Influential Than That of Financial Literacy and Self-Control.

Author and year of Publication	Title of the Paper	Design / Methodology / Approach	Contributions	Research Limitations / Implications	Practical Implications	Originality / Value / Results
Theme – 4: Impact of financial literacy on financial wellbeing of effective Debt management						
Edy Jumady, Hasbiyadi , Yaisa Anggraini, Yana Fajriah 29 th March 2024	The effect of financial planning on consumer debt management – the role of financial literacy, self-efficacy and financial motivation	Qualitative research design based on in-depth interviews with a randomly chosen sample	The relationship is multi-faceted, with financial literacy emerging as a foundational element that improves participants' debt management skills.	People don't want to admit they're in debt just yet. Getting people to fill out the surveys was a major challenge.	Improved Financial Well-Being is the Result of High Financial Self-Efficacy, Which is Influenced by Literacy and Motivates Proactive Financial Behaviors.	Finance education must be tailored to individual requirements and circumstances to enhance debt management and financial wellness. It will boost financial knowledge, self-confidence, and motivation.
Yulianah, Istiglaliyah	The Influence of Financial Literacy	Purposive Sampling Method	Debt Management behaviour is in low	Findings the respondents	Financial Literacy needs to be well	Financial literacy has a significant effect on

Muflikhati Jan 2023	and Lifestyle on Debt Management Behaviour in Young Married Families	used for data collection and analysed in Multiple Linear Regression Tests	category and there is a negative relationship between the respondents age and debt management behaviour	with managing the debt	owned in order to create good debt management behaviour	debt management behaviour
Carlander, A., Hauff, J. C 1 st January 2019	Financial Literacy and Debt	Discussed and assessed on the demographic factors impact of financial literacy on a Number of selected variables	The effect of financial literacy on a number of debt related financial behaviours such as . mortgage related decisions and use of credit cards, etc is more	Identifying the respondents with the knowledge of financial literacy with objective knowledge.	The Connection between the Literacy and Indebtedness for the group of young adults is also took for the consideration for analysis	There is a direct relationship between the literacy and indebtedness for the group of young adults

Author and year of Publication	Title of the Paper	Design / Methodology / Approach	Contributions	Research Limitations / Implications	Practical Implications	Originality / Value / Results
Theme – 5: Impact of financial literacy on financial well-being of better budgeting and financial control						
Syed Atif Ali, Sumaira Aslam, Muhammad Ussama Majeed, Muhammad Usman 19 th May 2024	The Interplay of Mental Budgeting, Self – Control and Financial Behaviour: Implications for Individual Financial Well-being	A self-administered Questionnaire was adapted to gather responses of the employees working in various organisations. PLS and SPSS were utilized for analysis	People are able to better their finances when they use mental budgeting	Making the people to understand about the Mental Budgeting and self-control	It clarifies how people can better manage their finance by both mental strategies and behavioural control	Factors that work together to influence the financial behaviour, highlighting need for more financial advice that considers mental budgeting and self-control
Dr. Pratima Rawal, Kitty Sandeep Rana Dec 2024	Analysing the Impact of Budgeting in Personal Finance amongst working Mumbaikars	The study employed a mixed method approach of combining surveys and interviews to explore the relationship	Many working Mumbaikars regular track their income and expenses	Limited number of sample size is undertaken for the study which may not be sufficient for making the decision	It Provides valuable insights for both Individuals and Policymakers	It emphasises the significance of financial literacy and tailored systems in improving personal financial management
Nataliia Versal, Ihor Honchar, Mariia Balytska, Vasyl Erastov 2023	How do Savings and Personal Budgeting Matter on Financial Literacy and Well – Being	Applied Pearson Pairwise Correlation between Nine Indicators of Personal Budgeting and Savings	GDP Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) per capital is Under the significant influence of all factors both in sample of countries	Financial Literacy Database started to be gathered relatively recently and are not regularly updated	The results of the study may have interest for policy makers since they focus on improvement of financial literacy	Understanding the interplay between the subjective and objective financial well-being of an individuals
Ruofan Bai 2023	Impact of Financial Literacy, Mental Budgeting and Self Control on Financial Wellbeing: Mediating impact of Investment Decision Making	The study employed partial Least Square structural Equation Modelling to analyse the sample of 449 University Students	Individuals who practice mental budgeting, a technique that entails mentally classifying and monitoring their expenditure, demonstrate elevated levels of Financial well-being	The study only aims at only cognitive factors like mental budgeting, self control	Feasible Perspectives for Policy makers, Financial Institutions, and Individuals to foster financial wellness and enhance financial results	The greater degree of financial literacy are more prone to achieving superior financial well-being

Vincent Gunawan, Vera Intanie Dewi, Triyana Iskandarsyah, Irsanti Hasyim June 2021	Women's Financial Literacy: Perceived Financial Knowledge and Its Impact on Money Management	The data collected through structured questionnaires in online from the baby boomer generations as well as Gen X< Y, Z.. data analysed using partial least squares structural equation Modeling	Women have an important role in managing family finances and their ability to conduct good financial management can help their family financial stability	The sample size collected for analysis may not be large enough to representative of entire population	The perceived financial knowledge has a significant effect on Financial Management behaviour in the dimension of savings, Shopping behaviour, long-term and short-term planning	There is a moderate level of financial literacy and financial management Behaviour
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Themes and their Relevant Studies

S.No	Themes	Relevant Studies
1	Conceptualisation of Financial Literacy	Dr. Vikas Mahadule, Mrs. Harsha Patil, Mr. Pavan Padghan, Mr. Saurav Temgire (5 th November 2024), Suhail Ahmad Bhat, Umer Mushtaq Lone, S. Arunkumar, U M Gopal Krishna (13 th November 2024), Jyothi Prakash Rath (April 2023), Rajesh Mishra (2022)
2	Impact of Financial Literacy on Financial well-being of Financial Decision Making	Mishra, Deepak, Naveen, Agrawal, Sanawi Sharahiley and Vinay Kandpal (17 th October 2024), Zaara Chowdhury (01 st November 2024), Dr. P. Chandrika Reddy, Shafiya Taj (8 th August 2024), Sonam Rani (14 th Sep 2023), Mubarakah Bunyamin, Nor SHaipah Abdul Wahab (30 th December 2022), Suresh G (23 rd August 2021),
3	Impact of Financial Literacy on Financial Well Being of Enhanced Savings and Investment Behaviour	Bangun Putra PRasetya (31 st July 2023), Seema Gupta (14 th April 2023), Godfred Matthew Yaw Owusu, Theodora Aba Abekah Koomson, (Et., Al) (14 th Jan 2022), Dr. Sukhpreet K Thind, Dr. Asim Ray (2023), Godfred Mattew Yaw Owusu, Theodora Aba Abekah Koomson, (Et., all) (11 th August 2023), Wagar Younas, Muhammad Farooq, (et, al) (20 th Jan 2019)
4	Impact of Financial Literacy on Financial Well Being of Effective Debt Management	Edy Jumady, Hasbiyadi , Yaisa Anggraini, Yana Fajriah (29 th March 2024), Yulianah, Istiglaliyah Muflikhati (Jan 2023), Carlander, A., Hauff, J. C (1 st January 2019)
5	Impact of Financial Literacy on Financial Well Being of Better Budgeting and Financial Control	Syed Atif Ali, Sumaira Aslam, Muhammad Ussama Majeed, Muhammad Usman (19 th May 2024), Dr. Pratima Rawal, Kitty Sandeep Rana (Dec 2024), Nataliia Versal, Ihor Honchar, Mariia Balytska, Vasyl Erastov (2023), Ruofan Bai (2023), Vincent Gunawan, Vera Intanie Dewi, Triyana Iskandarsyah, Irsanti Hasyim(June 2021)

Future Scope of the Study

The recommendations from the examined articles on the basis of selected agenda for future research on the relationship between Financial Literacy and Financial Well Being is to recommend the research scholars to investigate the impact of financial literacy on financial well being of Debt Management, Selb Budgeting and Financial Control. By conducting the studies on these areas, scholars can analyse the individual's financial control and Budgeting control factors of an Individuals are affecting by the financial literacy awareness. These insights will yield priceless factors of most successful interventions and how to modify them to suit the different needs of the different populations. Below are some areas where Scholars can contribute their research

- Tailored Courses on Money Management

- Technology-Enabled Money Management Resources and Education
- How Financial Literacy Affects Debt Management in the Context of Behavioral Finance
- Understanding Money Management and Taking Investment Risks

Conclusion

In order to better understand how financial literacy might lead to financial well-being, this study systematically looked at previous research on the topic. The goal was to identify important themes and identify areas for future research on the topic. Our findings provide satisfactory responses to the research questions.

Several Studies reviewed consistently revealed financial well being to significantly Influenced by Financial Literacy and having self-control has a good effect on financial well-being, while impulsivity has the opposite effect. (Jyothi Prakash Rath, (April 2023)). The following key themes were identified in the studies

- Conceptualisation of Financial Literacy
- Impact of financial literacy on financial wellbeing of financial decision making
- Impact of financial literacy on financial wellbeing of enhanced savings and investment behaviour
- Impact of Financial Literacy on financial well-being of Effective Debt Management
- Impact of Financial Literacy on financial well-being of Better Budgeting and Financial Control

The review serves as a core resource for ongoing studies into the relationship between Financial Literacy and Financial Well-Being and Presents more important suggestions for Future Research to enhance the knowledge in the area. The review as well discovered other variables to also have a pronounced effect on financial well-being. A limitation of the study is that it only included publications from the selected journals data base which has impact factor more than 1. Significant research that was released in other media or database (Such as Books, Conferences Proceedings, etc) was not Included. The criteria to remove the articles was subjectivity of the paper and relevance for the study.

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